

SHORT NOTES

Synthesis of 2'-Hydroxy-5'-nitro-3', 4'-benzo-chalkone Derivatives

B. J. Ghiya and M. G. Marathey

2-Hydroxy-3,4-benzo-5-nitroacetophenone was condensed with different aldehydes, viz., benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, and *m*- and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehydes with a view to studying the effect of the nitro group on the formation of chalcones and flavones. The condensation of these aldehydes with the ketone takes not less than 3 hours in presence of 40% NaOH. If sodium peroxide is used as a condensing agent, the aldehydes condense within 2 minutes to afford the chalcones. In the formation of chalcones sodium peroxide thus characterises itself in decreasing the reaction time to a minimum. The ease in which the condensation takes is in the order: *m*-hydroxy- > *p*-hydroxy- > *o*-hydroxy-aldehyde.

2-Hydroxy-5-nitro-3,4-benzoacetophenone (I).— α -Naphthol acetate (14.4g.) was subjected to the Fries migration in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (20 g.) by keeping the mixture for 1 hour at 120° in an oil bath. The complex was decomposed with water and HCl (dil.) and the crude mass was crystallised from dilute acetic acid as white crystals (10 g.), m.p. 96°. To 2-hydroxy-3,4-benzoacetophenone, dissolved in acetic acid (50 c.c.), HNO₃ (conc., 6 c.c.) was added dropwise with continuous stirring at a controlled temperature, not above 50°. Yellow needle-shaped crystals separated after 20 minutes, and stirring was continued for 15 another minutes. The crude mass after filtration at the pump was crystallised from acetic acid as straw-coloured needles (7g.), m.p. 162°. (Found: N, 5.8. Calc. N:6.0%). It dissolves in NaOH solution and develops a green colour with ethanolic ferric chloride.

Chalcones (II).—Ketone (I, 0.5 g.) and the corresponding aldehyde (1g.) were dissolved in ethanol (10 c.c.); 40% NaOH solution (2c.c.) was added to the boiling ethanolic solution. The solution was acidified after 3 hours and treated with boiling water to remove the

acid formed in the side reaction (sodium bicarbonate could not be used as it also dissolved the nitrochalkones) and the crude mass was crystallised from acetic acid; yield 0.25-0.3g. Only the chalkone of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde was crystallised from 50% acetic acid.

The following compounds have been prepared:

- (i) $R_1=R_2=R_3=H$, m.p. 208°.
- (ii) $R_1=OMe$, $R_2=R_3=H$, m.p. 204°.
- (iii) $R_3=OH$, $R_1=R_2=H$, m.p. 205°.
- (iv) $R_2=OH$, $R_1=R_3=H$, m.p. 211°.
- (v) $R_1=OH$, $R_2=R_3=H$, m.p. 158°.

Percentage of nitrogen is in accord with the value calculated on the basis of the expected composition.

The products obtained by the sodium hydroxide method were compared with those obtained by sodium peroxide method. The benzaldehyde and the *o*- and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehydes gave their respective acids in quantity more than the chalkones by sodium peroxide condensation. This is due to the easy oxidation of the aldehydes in presence of hydroxy group.

Chalkone Dibromides (III).—To the solution of the corresponding chalkone (0.01M) in chloroform (10c.c.) was added a 25% solution of bromine (0.01M) in chloroform. The mixture was kept for 2 hours when a solid separated which was filtered; yield 0.007-0.01 g. The following compounds were prepared:

- (i) $R_1=R_2=R_3=H$, m.p. 158°.
- (ii) $R_1=OMe$, $R_2=R_3=H$, m.p. 150°.
- (iii) $R_3=OH$, $R_1=R_2=H$, m.p. 190°.
- (iv) $R_2=OH$, $R_1=R_3=H$, m.p. 140°.
- (v) $R_1=OH$, $R_2=R_3=H$, m.p. 170°.

Percentage of bromine is in accord with the value calculated on the basis of the expected composition.

Flavones (IV).—The chalkone dibromide (1g.), suspended in ethanol (10c.c.), was treated with 2N-NaOH (5c.c.) solution. After 2 hrs. the crude mass was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid; yield 0.4-0.6g. The following compounds were prepared:

- (i) $R_1=R_2=R_3=H$, m.p. 226°.
- (ii) $R_1=OMe$, $R_2=R_3=H$, m.p. 228°.
- (iii) $R_3=OH$, $R_1=R_2=H$, m.p. 210°.
- (iv) $R_2=OH$, $R_1=R_3=H$, m.p. 234°.
- (v) $R_1=OH$, $R_2=R_3=H$, m.p. 240°.

The analytical data are in accord with those calculated on the expected composition.